

Molecular and crystalline architectures of a mononuclear nickel(II)azide compound containing an unsymmetrical bidentate Schiff base

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Manuscript received 18 August 2009, revised 3 March 2010, accepted 16 March 2010

Abstract : The mononuclear complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{pbba})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]$ (**1**) [pbba = *N*-((pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)benzylamine, ($\text{N}^1, \text{N}^{\text{P}}$); N^1 = imine N, N^{P} = pyridine N] has been isolated following an earlier procedure and structure is determined by X-ray diffraction technique. Single crystal structural analysis shows that the metal center in **1** adopts a distorted octahedral geometry with an NiN_6 chromophore ligated through four N atoms of two unsymmetrical ($\text{N}^1, \text{N}^{\text{P}}$) bidentate pbba units. The hexacoordination is completed by two N atoms (N^{A} 's) of terminal azides in mutual *cis* orientation. The gross geometry is a *cis, trans, cis* in the order (N^1, N^1), ($\text{N}^{\text{P}}, \text{N}^{\text{P}}$) and ($\text{N}^{\text{A}}, \text{N}^{\text{A}}$). Intermolecular weak C-H...N hydrogen bondings in **1** give rise to a 1D chain structure.

Keywords : Nickel(II), unsymmetrical bidentate Schiff base, synthesis, superstructure.

Introduction

The construction¹ of veritable molecular and crystalline architectures² with different shapes and sizes³ formed through control and manipulation of strong metal-ligand covalent bonds and multiple lateral weak non-covalent forces like hydrogen bonding⁴ $\pi \cdots \pi$ and C-H... π interactions⁵ have been examined extensively for the preparation of functional materials⁶⁻⁸. Self-assembly⁹ of the building units in pre-assigned ratios is used to prepare such metal-organic frameworks. Recently, we are active¹⁰⁻¹² in this approach for isolation of different polymers and polymer-based superstructures through variation of blocking and bridging ligand backbones and metal-ion coordination environments. Different transition and non-transition metal-ions are used as geometry setters, Schiff bases¹³ as end-capping units and pseudohalides^{14,15} as intermediaries. The study of mono- and polynuclear complexes of nickel(II) is an important objective because of their interesting synthetic, structural, spectroscopic, magnetic and optoelectronic features^{16,17}.

The present work originates from our interest to establish the molecular and crystalline architectures of a nickel(II) monomeric complex of the type $[\text{Ni}(\text{pbba})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]$

(**1**), [pbba = *N*-((pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)benzylamine] obtained from condensation of 1 : 1 molar ratio of 2-benzoylpyridine and benzylamine. The complex **1** was reported¹² earlier and characterized using microanalytical, spectroscopic, magnetic and other physicochemical results. But the exact coordination environment and long-range structure in crystalline state are not known, as it seems to be very difficult to grow single crystals of the compound. After several attempts we have isolated suitable X-ray quality single crystals. The structure of **1** is identified using X-ray diffraction measurement which reveals that the gross geometry is *cis, trans, cis* in the order (N^1, N^1), ($\text{N}^{\text{P}}, \text{N}^{\text{P}}$) and ($\text{N}^{\text{A}}, \text{N}^{\text{A}}$) (N^{A} = azide N; Scheme 1) The mononuclear units of **1** pack through doubly weak C-H...N hydrogen bonds affording a supramolecular 1D chain.

(pbba ; $\text{N}^1, \text{N}^{\text{P}}$)

Scheme 1. Possible geometrical isomers in $[\text{Ni}(\text{N}^i, \text{N}^P)_2(\text{N}_3)_2]$ (1).

Results and discussion

During our earlier work¹², the complex was prepared using a 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratio of nickel(II) nitrate/acetate/perchlorate, pbba and NaN_3 in methanolic solution; but it was not possible to isolate suitable single crystals for X-ray crystallographic study. Changing the metal salt to nickel(II) chloride the reactions were carried out in various solvent mixtures such as MeOH-MeCN (3 : 1, 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3), MeOH-DMF (3 : 1, 2 : 1 and 1 : 1) and MeOH-MeCN-DMF (3 : 1 : 1, 2 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1) at room temperature. We were able to grow single crys-

tals of $[\text{Ni}(\text{pbba})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]$ (1) suitable for X-ray crystallographic analysis from the solvent mixture MeOH-MeCN-DMF (2 : 2 : 1). The bidentate Schiff base contains unsymmetrical (N^i, N^P) donor centers. Complex of type $[\text{Ni}(\text{N}^i, \text{N}^P)_2(\text{N}_3)_2]$ with unsymmetrical bidentate blocking ligand and symmetric homoatomic pseudohalide can, in principle¹⁸, give rise to five molecular architectures (Scheme 1). To learn which one in Scheme 1 is isolated, X-ray diffraction measurement of 1 was done.

An ORTEP diagram with atom numbering scheme of 1 is shown in Fig. 1. Selected bond lengths and angles

Fig. 1. ORTEP diagram of $[\text{Ni}(\text{pbba})_2(\text{N}_3)_2]$ (1) with atom labeling scheme and 20% probability ellipsoids for all non-hydrogen atoms.

relevant to the coordination spheres are listed in Table 1. The metal center adopts a distorted octahedral geometry

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for 1

Bond distances :			
Ni(1)-N(1)	2.0592(9)	Ni(1)-N(1*)	2.0592(9)
Ni(1)-N(2)	2.1149(10)	Ni(1)-N(2*)	2.1149(10)
N(4)-N(5)	1.162(2)	Ni(1)-N(3*)	2.1021(13)
Bond angles :			
N(1)-Ni(1)-N(2)	78.45(4)	N(2)-Ni(1)-N(3*)	171.53(4)
N(1)-Ni(1)-N(3)	91.29(5)	N(3)-Ni(1)-N(1*)	94.21(5)
N(1)-Ni(1)-N(1*)	172.18(4)	N(3)-Ni(1)-N(2*)	171.53(4)
N(1)-Ni(1)-N(2*)	96.44(4)	N(3)-Ni(1)-N(3*)	90.68(5)
N(1)-Ni(1)-N(3*)	94.21(5)	N(1*)-Ni(1)-N(2*)	78.45(4)
N(2)-Ni(1)-N(3)	85.32(5)	N(1*)-Ni(1)-N(3*)	91.29(5)
N(2)-Ni(1)-N(1*)	96.44(4)	N(2*)-Ni(1)-N(3*)	85.32(5)
N(2)-Ni(1)-N(2*)	99.60(4)	N(3)-N(4)-N(5)	178.57(17)

with a NiN₆ chromophore ligated by two bidentate Schiff bases (pbba's) and two terminal azides. The coordination includes two pyridine N^P atoms [N(1), N(1*)] and two

85.32(5)°] are very close to 360.00°. So the N(2), N(2*), N(3), N(3*) and Ni(1) atoms are almost on a same plane. The azides are almost linear with N-N-N angle 178.57(17)° and mutually in *cis* alignment with N(3)-Ni(1)-N(3*) angle 90.68(5)°.

In the crystal packing the terminal azide nitrogen [N(5)] and aromatic hydrogen [H(11)] of benzene ring of the Schiff base, pbba are involved in doubly weak C-H...N hydrogen bonds [C(11)-H(11A)...N(5) : C(11)-H(11) : 0.9300 Å; H(11)...N(5) : 2.5500 Å; C(11)...N(5) : 3.347(2) Å; <C(11)-H(11)-N(5): 144.00°] among the mononuclear units to give an infinite 1D chain (Fig. 2) along crystallographic *c*-axis. The molecular architecture corresponding to *cis*, *trans*, *cis* geometry in the order (Nⁱ,Nⁱ), (N^P,N^P) and (N^a,N^a) (Scheme 1) ensures such double C-H...N hydrogen bondings.

In summary, we are able to isolate and characterize a new crystalline architecture of a mononuclear nickel(II)azide in concert with an unsymmetrical bidentate Schiff base.

Fig. 2. 1D supramolecular chain in 1 formed by doubly C-H...N hydrogen bondings.

imine Nⁱ atoms [N(2), N(2*)] of two different blockers along with two terminal azido N^a atoms [N(3), N(3*)]. The nitrogen atoms N(2), N(2*), N(3) and N(3*) define the equatorial plane around nickel(II), whereas the axial sites are occupied by N(1) and N(1*). The distortion from ideal octahedral geometry is due to the asymmetric nature of the bound Schiff base and the deviations of the refine angles (90°/180°) formed at the metal center (Table 1). The sum (360.92°) of the equatorial angles [N(3)-Ni(1)-N(3*) 90.68(5)°, N(3*)-Ni(1)-N(2*) 85.32(5)°, N(2*)-Ni(1)-N(2) 99.60(4)° and N(2)-Ni(1)-N(3)

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity benzylamine (Lancaster, UK), 2-benzoylpyridine (Lancaster, UK), nickel(II) chloride (E. Merck, India) and sodium azide (E. Merck, India) were purchased from respective concerns and were used as received. The Schiff base, pbba was synthesized by reported procedure¹². All other chemicals and solvents were AR grade and were used as received. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air.

Elemental analyses, IR spectra, molar conductance,

room temperature magnetic susceptibility of powdered sample, electrochemical study, ground state absorption study, steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence measurements were carried out as described elsewhere¹².

Preparation of the complex :

[Ni(pbba)₂(N₃)₂] (1) : The complex was prepared by a reported method¹² with a little modification to isolate it in crystalline form. NiCl₂·6H₂O (237 mg, 1 mmol) dissolved in MeOH-MeCN solvent mixture (15 ml) was added to the DMF solution (5 ml) of pbba (545 mg, 2 mmol). To this mixture a methanolic solution (5 ml) of NaN₃ (130 mg, 2 mmol) was added dropwise. The final reddish brown solution was filtered and left for slow evaporation in air at room temperature. After 2 days, fine reddish brown crystals of 1 were isolated by filtration, washed with methanol and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield, 549 mg (80%). Microanalytical, IR, UV-Vis-spectroscopic, magnetic (μ_{eff}) and electrochemical (E^0) results were checked and found to be akin to those obtained elsewhere¹².

X-Ray crystallographic analysis :

Single crystals of 1 were obtained by slow evaporation of MeOH-MeCN-DMF (2 : 2 : 1) solution mixture. Diffraction data at 293 K for 1 were collected on a Siemens SMART CCD diffractometer using Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The crystal data and data collection parameters are listed in Table 2. Of the 46971 unique reflections, 5935 with $I > 2\sigma(I)$ were used for structure solutions. The structure was solved by direct methods, and the structure solution and refinement were based on $|F|^2$ using SHELXL-97¹⁹. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters whereas hydrogen atoms were placed in calculated positions when possible and given isotropic U values 1.2 times that of the atom to which they are bonded. The final differences Fourier map showed the maximum and minimum peak heights at 0.18 and -0.15 e\AA^{-3} . All calculations were carried out using PLATON²⁰ and ORTEP-32²¹.

Supplementary data :

Crystallographic data (excluding structure factors) for 1 has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre No. CCDC 730369. Copies of this information can be obtained, free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12, Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : +44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

Table 2. Crystallographic data for [Ni(pbba)₂(N₃)₂] (1)

Crystallographic parameter :	1
Empirical formula	C ₃₈ H ₃₂ N ₁₀ Ni
Formula weight	687.43
Temperature (K)	293
Wavelength (\AA)	0.71073
Crystal system	Orthorhombic
Space group	Fdd2
D (calc) [g/cm ³]	1.389
Volume (\AA^3)	6573.61(16)
Z	8
Unit cell dimensions :	
a (\AA)	16.6032(2)
b (\AA)	44.0861(8)
c (\AA)	8.9807(1)
α ($^\circ$), β ($^\circ$), γ ($^\circ$)	90, 90, 90
$F(000)$	2864
μ (Mo-K α) (mm ⁻¹)	0.636
θ range for data collection ($^\circ$)	1.9, 32.5
$h/k/l$	-24,24/-66,66/-13,13
Reflections collected	46971
Independent reflections	5935
Data/restraints/parameters	5935/1/222
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.026
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.0275
R indices (all data)	0.036
Largest peak and hole (e\AA^{-3})	-0.15, 0.18
$R = \sum F_o - F_c / \sum F_o $, $wR = [\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / \sum w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}$, calcd. $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0344P)^2 + 1.3750P]$ (1), where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$.	

Acknowledgement

Financial support from the UGC, New Delhi, India is gratefully acknowledged. Thanks are due to Prof. H.-K. Fun, X-Ray Crystallography Unit, School of Physics, Universiti Sains Malaysia, 11800 USM, Penang, Malaysia for helping X-ray data collection. KB and SK thank the CSIR for fellowships.

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